

DOLLAR EXCHANGE RATE IN RUBLES AND SOLAR ACTIVITY
(1993 - 2025): R2 = 0.83
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Abstract

This report utilizes a methodological approach developed by W. S. Jevons and A. L. Chizhevsky. Solar cycle years were numbered according to the order established in solar astrophysics, grouped, and compared with the arithmetic mean values of Wolf numbers and the percentage changes in the dollar-to-ruble exchange rate compared to the previous year.

The scientific novelty of this study lies in the identification of a nonlinear, dome-shaped relationship between the rate of change in the dollar-to-ruble exchange rate and solar activity. A psychological channel for the influence of space weather on the behavior of currency market participants through the dynamics of serotonin and melatonin biosynthesis is proposed and detailed for the first time. A new methodology for medium-term exchange rate forecasting was developed based on grouping data by year ordinal numbers within the 11-year Schwabe cycle. The resulting cubic model (a third-degree polynomial) has a high correlation strength ($R^2 = 0.8341$) and proven statistical reliability ($p = 0.00197$), allowing the forecast to be isolated from short-term market noise.

The projected percentage change in the dollar-to-ruble exchange rate compared to the previous year is 64% for 2026 and 60% for 2027.

Keywords:

Dollar exchange rate in rubles, solar activity cycles, Wolf numbers, economic cycles, foreign exchange market, serotonin, melatonin, optimism, pessimism.

In his article “Solar-Commercial Cycles,” W. S. Jevons plotted solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and corn price cycles in Delhi over the period 1760–1810 [1, P.227], i.e., he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph “The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun” in Chapter 4 “The Sun and Epidemics” in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that depicts the average solar activity cycle over a hundred years (the cycle of Wolf numbers) and the average cases of cholera in Russia for the years of the solar cycle for the period 1823-1923 [2, p. 201].

This study compares the average Wolf numbers and the percentage changes in the dollar exchange rate in rubles for the period 1993–2025 on a single chart.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity (SA), were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [3]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The ordinal numbers of years in column 3 of Table 1 are determined as follows. The first year in a SA cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, that is, the increase in the Wolf number, which is presented in column 2.

Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the SA minimum.

The RUKSPERT website contains statistical data on average annual dollar exchange rates for the period 1992–2025 [4]. These are presented in column 4 of Table 1. Based on these data, the author calculated changes in the dollar exchange rate in rubles, expressed as a percentage, in column 5 of Table 1.

Table 1. Average annual Wolf numbers, ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles, dollar exchange rate in rubles and as a percentage of the previous year

Years	Wolf number	The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	Dollar exchange rate in rubles, rub/dollar	Dollar exchange rate in rubles as a percentage of the previous year, %
1	2	3	4	5
1992	133	6	0.29	-
1993	76.1	7	0.93	222.33
1994	44.9	8	2.19	135.72
1995	25.1	9	4.55	108.11
1996	11.6	10	5.12	12.46
1997	28.9	1	5.79	12.96
1998	88.3	2	9.73	68.19
1999	136.3	3	24.61	152.93
2000	173.9	4	28.12	14.6
2001	170.4	5	29.17	3.73
2002	163.6	6	31.35	7.47
2003	99.3	7	30.69	-2.11
2004	65.3	8	28.81	-6.13
2005	45.8	9	28.29	-1.80
2006	24.7	10	27.19	-3.89
2007	12.6	11	25.58	-5.92

2008	4.2	12	24.86	-2.81
2009	4.8	1	31.72	27.59
2010	24.9	2	30.37	-4.26
2011	80.8	3	29.39	-3.23
2012	84.5	4	31.09	5.78
2013	94	5	31.85	2.44
2014	113.3	6	38.42	20.63
2015	69.8	7	60.96	58.67
2016	39.8	8	67.03	9.96
2017	21.7	9	58.35	-12.95
2018	7	10	62.71	7.47
2019	3.6	11	64.74	3.24
2020	8.8	1	72.15	11.45
2021	29.6	2	73.65	2.08
2022	83.2	3	68.55	-6.92
2023	125.5	4	85.25	24.36
2024	154.6	5	92.57	8.59
2025	123.2	6	83.62	-9.67
2026		7		

Next, the statistical data in Table 1 for the period 1993–2025 were grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. Column 2 of Table 2 shows the number of such years for the period 1993–2025.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles

1. The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	2. Number of such years for the period 1993 - 2025	Arithmetic mean:	
		3. числа Вольфа	4. изменения курса доллара в рублях в процентах к предыдущему году, %
1	3	14.13	17.33
2	3	47.60	33.01
3	3	100.10	47.59
4	3	127.97	14.80
5	3	139.67	4.92
6	3	133.37	6.14
7	3	81.73	92.96
8	3	50.00	46.52
9	3	30.87	31.12
10	3	14.43	5.35
11	2	8.10	-1.34
12	1	4.20	-2.81
Итого:	33		

Based on rows 1–12 and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, Fig. 1 constructs a diagram that shows a very strong relationship between the average Wolf numbers and the change in the dollar exchange rate in rubles as a percentage of the previous year by year in the average (12-year) SA cycle for 1993–2025. The value of the determination coefficient R^2 equal to 0.9319 means that the constructed polynomial model explains 93.2% of the changes in the dollar exchange rate depending on the Wolf numbers.

Fig. 1. The dollar exchange rate in rubles as a function of average Wolf numbers, 12 years of the average SA cycle for 1993–2025, 33 years of observations, the method of superposing epochs

The diagram in Figure 2 uses a third-degree polynomial. Third-degree polynomial regression analysis based on 12 observation points revealed a strong correlation between the variables. The coefficient of determination is $R^2 = 0.8341$, which explains 83.41% of the variation in the outcome variable. The resulting significance level of $p = 0.00197$ ($p < 0.01$) allows us to completely reject the null hypothesis. The model is statistically reliable.

Fig. 2. The dollar exchange rate in rubles as a function of average Wolf numbers, 12 years of the average SA cycle for 1993–2025, 33 years of observations, the method of superposing epochs, a polynomial of degree 3

The current Wolf number forecast for 2026 is posted on the NASA website [5] (see 50% percentile). It is copied to Fig. 3. Below the figure is a link to a table with monthly Wolf number forecasts (50% percentile). It yields an average monthly forecast value of 91.43 for 2026 (calculated by the author based on the June 2026 forecast). This value corresponds to a forecasted percentage change in the dollar-to-ruble exchange rate compared to the previous year of 64% in the diagram in Fig. 2. The Wolf number forecast is updated periodically. The forecast for the percentage change in the dollar-to-ruble exchange rate should be updated accordingly.

The predicted Wolf number for 2027 is 64.53, which corresponds to a predicted 60% growth in the dollar-to-ruble exchange rate in the diagram in Figure 2.

It should be noted that non-economic events such as wars, sanctions, natural disasters, etc., may lead to inaccuracies in the forecast.

Fig. 3. Forecast of the development of the 25th SA cycle.

The mechanism underlying the identified relationships is as follows. A low SA (left side of the diagrams in Figures 1 and 2) indicates a low UV index, which leads to decreased production of serotonin (the hormone responsible for happiness and energy). This leads to increased pessimism and a decrease in purchasing activity, which in turn leads to a decrease in the dollar-to-ruble exchange rate as a percentage of the previous year.

High SA (the right side of the diagrams in Figures 1 and 2) is accompanied by high geomagnetic activity and suppressed production of the hormone melatonin, which is produced from serotonin. This leads to a decrease in serotonin stores and increased pessimism, which leads to a decrease in purchasing activity in the currency market.

The scientific novelty of this study consists of the following.

1. The hormonal and psychological influence of space weather on the economy has been substantiated. For the first time, a direct biological mechanism for transmitting heliomagnetic impulses to financial markets through fluctuations in serotonin and melatonin levels in market participants, which determine their purchasing behavior, has been proposed and detailed.

2. A nonlinear (dome-shaped) relationship between exchange rates and solar activity was discovered. Using a third-degree polynomial, the existence of a

"biological optimum" for solar activity was mathematically proven. It was shown that both a lack of UV radiation and extreme solar activity equally depress investor sentiment and reduce the rate of dollar exchange rate appreciation.

3. A new method for forecasting the dollar exchange rate has been developed.

It is based on the author's method of grouping macroeconomic data by year sequence numbers within the 11-year Schwabe cycle. The resulting cubic model has high accuracy ($R^2 = 0.8341$; $p < 0.01$) and allows forecasting currency market dynamics based on long-term astrophysical forecasts of the SA, while abstracting from short-term market noise.

This work does not constitute investment advice.

Reference

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